

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

A Framework Analysis of European Legal Entities

Complementary Paper of Deliverable 10.2
“Governance Model of the legal entity”

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Abstract

This Complementary Paper presents the results of the research carried out to assess the potential legal forms of the future European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). The investigation examines the governance and legal options, with particular attention to the extent to which different legal forms can support sustainability, transnational coordination, institutional legitimacy, and operational flexibility.

In relation to the research design, the team investigates how existing European research and digital infrastructures have addressed challenges related to governance, funding, administrative capacity, and cross-border interoperability through different legal configurations – focusing in particular on AISBLs and comparable Association/Foundation models, ERICs, and EDICs. The study adopts a qualitative comparative research design based on 15 semi-structured expert interviews conducted between December 2025 and February 2026 with representatives of major European infrastructures and organisations.

The interviews were analysed through framework analysis combining deductive and inductive coding procedures, enabling systematic cross-case comparison while preserving contextual diversity and emergent themes. The findings show that AISBL and association-based models provide high organisational flexibility and accessibility but remain vulnerable to administrative fragmentation and financial instability. ERICs offer the strongest framework for long-term institutional legitimacy and Member State commitment, although they require complex and negotiation-intensive establishment processes. EDICs emerge as governance-flexible and politically strategic instruments for European digital infrastructures, balancing adaptability with stronger governmental coordination, while raising unresolved questions concerning regulatory implementation and sustainability.

By identifying the respective advantages and limitations of each model, the findings provide an empirical basis for informing the strategic choice of the future legal entity of the Cloud.

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Existing Legal Entities for the Cultural Heritage Cloud

As future digital ecosystem for communities of the Cultural Heritage field, the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) aims at providing heritage professionals and researchers a Single-Entry-Point to access data, tools and resources. Given the complexity and diversity of the sector and its requirements, Work Package 10 “Cloud Governance” and specifically Task 10.2 “Governance Model of the legal entity” defines the legal framework that will constitute the governance of the platform, thus forming the backbone of its future services and tools.

A benchmarking exercise conducted in T10.2 showed that the following European legal entities are both suitable and available for the Cultural Heritage Cloud: Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (AISBL) under Belgium law, Association/Foundation under Dutch law, European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), and European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC).

To assess these options thoroughly and examine which legal entity best aligns with the future ECCCH ecosystem, qualitative expert interviews were held to deepen the analysis and expand on the results of the desktop research by consulting representatives of selected organisations corresponding to the entity models under study. Based on a structured research interview template (Rashidi et al.,2014), the interviews were designed to address areas that required further understanding and to gather the experts’ individual insights, particularly regarding the processes involved in establishing a legal entity, and not limited to its final form.

This Complementary Paper of Deliverable 10.2 outlines the framework analysis of the possible legal forms for the Cultural Heritage Cloud, supporting the process of determining the most suitable governance model.

Methodology of the Framework Analysis

Data Collection Process

From December 2025 to February 2026, 15 experts (partly ECHOES partners) across the four entity models ERIC, EDIC, AISBL under Belgian law, and Foundation/Association under Dutch law were interviewed by the ECHOES Consortium.

Participating organisations include ALT-EDIC, APEF, ARIADNE, CLARIN, DARIAH, DIGITAL COMMONS, EBRAINS, E.C.C.O., EF, ENA, ENCATC, EOSC, E-RIHS, MCA and OPERAS (see Table 1).

LEGAL ENTITY FORM		ORGANISATION/INSTITUTION
1	ERIC	E-RIHS
2	ERIC	DARIAH
3	ERIC	CLARIN
4	EDIC	ALT-EDIC
5	EDIC	DIGITAL COMMONS
6	EDIC	EBRAINS
7	AISBL	European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), OPERAS
8	AISBL	Michael Culture Association (MCA)
9	AISBL	ARIADNE
10	AISBL	European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisation (ECCO 1)
11	AISBL	European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisation (ECCO 2)
12	AISBL	European Network on Cultural Management and Policy -(ENCATC)
13	Foundations/Associations under Dutch law	Europeana Foundation (EF)
14	Foundations/Associations under Dutch law	Europeana Network Association(ENA)
15	Foundations/Associations under Dutch law	Archives Portal Europe Foundation (APEF)

Table 1 - Research sample (Source: authors' elaboration)

The interview template consisted of 11 questions, five sub-questions, and one optional question, where time allowed it. Structured into three phases – before, during, and after the establishment of the legal entity – the questions dealt with a wide range of topics, from administrative and operational requirements to governance and business models, as well as cooperation frameworks. A minimum of two interviewers were assigned per interview, with a duration of approximately 45 minutes per expert, or up to 90 minutes in the case of group interviews conducted with experts who are also ECHOES partners.

All sessions were recorded, transcribed, or documented through minutes, and subsequently stored in the project’s collaborative file system to ensure systematic analysis and reuse of the findings.

Data Coding Process

From a methodological perspective, the study design aligns with the conditions under which framework analysis is most effective, namely the presence of clearly defined research questions, a purposively structured sample, and the need for systematic cross-case comparison (Gale et al., 2013; Ritchie et al., 2014; Srivastava & Thomson, 2009). The coding process was grounded in the canonical stages of qualitative analysis (familiarisation, thematic framework development, indexing, charting, and mapping/interpretation), implemented through an iterative and recursive procedure rather than a linear progression.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the process comprised three sequential coding phases, each serving as a preparatory step for the subsequent interpretation of the findings. An initial coding framework was developed deductively, drawing on the interview guide and the analytical requirements of Deliverable 10.2 (Phase 1). This framework encompassed key dimensions such as the rationale for selecting a specific legal form, alternative options considered, implementation challenges, governance structures, user participation, operational needs, funding models, cross-border implications, involvement of third countries, potential evolution of legal status, and recommendations for future European entities.

The framework was subsequently refined through an inductive process (Phase 2), based on repeated examination of the full set of interview materials and the synthetic clustering table. This iterative analysis enabled the identification of recurrent sub-themes emerging directly from the data, including constraints related to banking and anti-money-laundering regulations, the influence of host-country administrative cultures, transitional or bridging organisational arrangements, hybrid funding configurations, distributed staffing models, and tensions between organisational flexibility and administrative burden. The integration of deductive and inductive approaches is consistent with established qualitative methodologies, such as framework analysis and thematic analysis, and ensured comparability across interviews while preserving the capacity to capture emergent and unanticipated findings (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Gale et al., 2013).

After coding, the material was charted into a comparative matrix (Phase 3) in which interview cases were categorized across shared analytical themes, and themes were read back against individual cases. In line with the framework approach, the matrix functioned as a structured display that preserved contextual nuance while making comparison possible both within and across legal models. The clustering was therefore carried out at two levels: first, within each legal category to identify recurring patterns and divergences among similar entities; second, across themes to determine which issues were structurally decisive for the legal entity of the future Cloud.

Figure 1 – Phases of the coding process

The final stage of analysis did not aggregate all interviews into a single averaged position. Instead, it retained convergences, divergences, and outlier perspectives as analytically relevant. Accordingly, the clustering of interviews went beyond a descriptive synthesis of responses and enabled a structured comparative interpretation of how different legal forms perform in practice with respect to establishment, governance, staffing, funding, legal interoperability, and long-term sustainability (Flick, 2022; Gale et al., 2013).

Comparative Exploitation of the Legal Entities

Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (AISBL) under Belgium Law

Across the AISBL interviews, a consistent pattern emerges: this legal form is primarily valued for its flexibility, its relatively accessible establishment process, and the symbolic as well as practical advantages associated with a Brussels-based seat, including European visibility, perceived diplomatic neutrality, and the capacity to accommodate international membership. This positive assessment is particularly evident in the EOSC/OPERAS, MCA, ARIADNE, and ENCATC interviews, which characterise the AISBL as an adaptable legal vehicle that can be configured to support diverse governance arrangements and partner constellations. At the same time, the analysis indicates that the practical viability of the model depends significantly on the availability of local administrative support. Recurring points of friction include Belgian banking procedures, publication and transparency requirements, anti-money-laundering compliance, and the need to rely on local accountants, notaries, or administrative intermediaries, as well as, in some cases, French-language administrative obligations. These challenges are particularly pronounced in the ECCO interviews, where the absence of stable local capacity has elevated administrative compliance to a strategic concern.

Governance across the AISBL cases is generally member-driven rather than strongly formalised in statutory terms: general assemblies and boards constitute the core decision-making bodies, while user participation is typically mediated through membership structures, service boards, working groups, or assemblies of commons, rather than through dedicated standalone user committees. From a financial perspective, however, the cluster reveals a structural limitation: the AISBL model functions effectively when supported either by stable membership-based revenue or by a deliberately lean organisational configuration, but becomes considerably more vulnerable when reliant on project-based funding streams. Overall, the AISBL emerges as a viable and highly flexible legal form for European networks and coordination structures; however, it does not constitute an inherently optimal long-term solution for

ECHOES, as several interviewees explicitly associate its advantages with unresolved issues related to financial sustainability, cross-border staffing, and recurring compliance costs.

Associations/Foundations under Dutch Law

The interviews with the Europeana Foundation (EF), the Europeana Network Association (ENA), and the Archives Portal Europe Foundation (APEF) indicate that associations and foundations established under Dutch law can offer flexible, independent, and operationally pragmatic legal frameworks for European cultural heritage organisations. EF underscores the advantages of the foundation model in terms of institutional autonomy, non-profit orientation, capacity to employ staff, and ability to attract and manage funding. ENA, by contrast, demonstrates the relevance of the association model in fostering democratic participation and structured community representation, albeit with continued operational reliance on EF.

APEF further shows that the Dutch foundation model may be particularly appropriate in contexts where public institutions, such as national archives, encounter legal or administrative constraints in joining membership-based associations.

Across the three cases, governance arrangements are characterised by a combination of formal statutory bodies, advisory or representative mechanisms, and active thematic or operational working groups. At the same time, the interviews highlight a set of recurring challenges, including structural dependence on EU and project-based funding streams, constrained internal administrative capacity, and the legal and administrative complexity associated with cross-border employment. Overall, these models appear effective in supporting openness, institutional independence, and community engagement; however, their suitability for a future Cloud legal entity would depend on the establishment of robust financial safeguards and clearly defined governance structures to ensure long-term sustainability.

European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)

Across the ERIC interviews, the predominant finding is that the ERIC model is selected when long-term commitment by Member States, cross-border legitimacy, and a clearly defined European public-interest mandate outweigh considerations of speed or administrative simplicity. E-RIHS, DARIAH, and CLARIN consistently associate the added value of the ERIC framework with sustained intergovernmental engagement and with the capacity to organise distributed research infrastructures within a formally recognised European legal structure. The analysis also indicates that this added value is accompanied by a lengthy and negotiation-intensive establishment phase. E-RIHS

emphasises how divergent regulatory interpretations and the temporary withdrawal of ICCROM contributed to procedural delays, while DARIAH highlights the importance of intermediary governance arrangements and transitional funding mechanisms to ensure continuity between project-based development and formal legal establishment. CLARIN further notes that the degree of familiarity of the host country with the ERIC legal form has a significant impact on subsequent operational efficiency.

A second recurring theme concerns the tension between European-level status and national-level implementation. Although the ERIC provides a shared legal and political framework, key operational domains—including human resources, VAT, accounting practices, and employment regulations—remain strongly influenced by the legal system and administrative culture of the host country. As a result, fragmentation is mitigated but not entirely eliminated.

Governance arrangements are consequently multi-layered and relatively formalised, typically comprising a General Assembly, national coordination structures, scientific and/or ethics advisory bodies, and thematic or technical working groups; dedicated user committees appear to play a less central role than more institutionalised forms of community representation. From a financial perspective, the model is characterised by hybrid funding configurations rather than reliance on a single revenue source, combining membership contributions, in-kind national inputs, host-country support, and European project funding. Overall, the ERIC cluster depicts this model as a robust and credible long-term legal framework for mature distributed research infrastructures, contingent upon the early availability of adequate political support, administrative capacity, and transitional funding.

European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)

Across the EDIC interviews, the clustering points to a model that is perceived as politically strategic, governance-flexible, and comparatively rapid to formalise once Member State alignment has been achieved, but still institutionally demanding in practice. ALT-EDIC presents the EDIC as the natural vehicle for a project conceived from the outset to connect governments and industry; Digital Commons frames it as a source of institutional capital capable of making a durable promise to users through Member State commitment; and EBRAINS describes the move from AISBL to EDIC as a strategically encouraged transition by the European Commission, expected to strengthen European positioning and improve access to dedicated calls. A recurring theme is that the decisive challenge lies less in the formal act of establishment than in the preceding political and administrative work: convincing states, identifying the

relevant ministerial interlocutors, developing statutes and governance files, and, where necessary, creating national implementing vehicles able to handle bank accounts, contracts, and financial flows.

The clustering also shows that EDIC governance is regarded as highly adaptable, but that this flexibility must be balanced against two major risks: bureaucratic drift on the one hand, and insufficient protection of user or research interests on the other. This tension appears clearly in the contrast between Digital Commons' insistence that founders should remain in a minority position vis-à-vis users, ALT-EDIC's multi-level state-industry architecture, and EBRAINS' emphasis on scientific governance, ethics, intellectual-property issues, and research-appropriate performance indicators. Financial sustainability is generally expected to rest on a mixed model combining Member State contributions and European projects, with possible openings to public-private cooperation, while unresolved questions remain around VAT treatment, economic activity, ownership and control requirements, and the fit between EDIC performance frameworks and research infrastructures.

Overall, the EDIC cluster suggests a promising model for politically backed, mission-driven European infrastructures, especially where coordination with Member States and industry is central, but one whose effectiveness depends on careful institutional design and strong pre-establishment negotiation.

Transversal Summary of Interview Exploitations and Concluding Remarks

The previous paragraphs presented the results of the framework analysis, highlighting converging and diverging patterns across the legal forms examined, particularly regarding governance flexibility, political legitimacy, administrative complexity, and long-term sustainability of European research and digital infrastructures. The AISBL and related Association/Foundation models emerge as highly flexible and relatively accessible legal forms, particularly suited to European networks requiring operational autonomy, international visibility, and adaptable governance structures. Their effectiveness depends, however, on stable administrative support and sustainable financial models, as reliance on project-based funding and cross-border compliance obligations may generate structural vulnerabilities.

The ERIC model is consistently associated with long-term institutional stability, strong Member State commitment, and high European legitimacy for distributed research infrastructures.

While governance structures are robust and multi-layered, the establishment process is lengthy and administratively demanding, requiring sustained political support, transitional funding, and alignment with national legal systems.

EDICs are perceived as politically strategic and governance-flexible instruments capable of rapidly consolidating European digital infrastructures once Member State consensus is achieved. Their added value lies in combining governmental coordination, mission-oriented governance, and potential public-private cooperation, although important challenges remain regarding institutional complexity, implementation capacity, and financial and regulatory sustainability.

Legal form	Main Implementation or operational challenges	Governance and funding implications
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AISBL

The main difficulties concerned Belgian administrative procedures, banking requirements, language barriers, notarial obligations, transparency and anti-money-laundering requirements, and the need for local legal or administrative support. Some organisations found the set-up manageable and fast, while others experienced significant operational friction, especially when they lacked staff or presence in Belgium.

AISBLs allow flexible governance structures, including General Assemblies, boards, working groups, scientific or advisory committees and member-based representation. Funding models vary widely: some depend heavily on membership fees, others on EU projects, services, inventories, or mixed public-private sources. Project dependency was often seen as unstable, and HR or employment arrangements across countries were identified as a recurring issue.

Foundations/Associations under Dutch law

Implementation was generally less politically complex than ERIC or EDIC processes, but challenges included choosing the most appropriate national legal framework, negotiating differentiated financial contributions, managing dependency on another organisation, and dealing with limited capacity to generate income directly from content or activities.

These structures can support transparent governance, independent boards, democratic member councils and lightweight operational arrangements. Funding tends to rely on institutional contributions, European Commission contracts, project funding, membership-related mechanisms, or support from a parent/foundation structure. Long-term sustainability may be vulnerable when funding depends heavily on one contract, one institution or one external funding stream.

ERIC

The establishment process was generally described as long, negotiation-intensive, and

ERICs require a strong administrative core, formal governance bodies such as a

	<p>politically demanding. Key hurdles included the need to secure Member State commitment, bridge the gap between project funding and legal establishment, manage host-country legal issues, and deal with national rules on HR, VAT, accounting, and administration. Statute changes may also become difficult as membership grows.</p>	<p>General Assembly, Board of Directors and Scientific Advisory Board, as well as national coordination structures. Funding generally combines membership fees, in-kind contributions, national support, and EU projects. Membership fees alone are usually insufficient, making funding diversification important.</p>
<p>EDIC</p>	<p>The EDIC model was described as promising but still relatively new. Challenges included convincing Member States, identifying the right ministerial contacts, negotiating statutes and governance documents, and clarifying unresolved issues around VAT, state aid, economic activity, KPIs and national implementation structures. In some cases, an additional national legal vehicle was needed to operate locally.</p>	<p>EDIC governance was seen as flexible and adaptable, but it requires careful design to avoid excessive bureaucracy or founder capture. Funding models combine Member State contributions, EU projects, national or institutional support and, in some cases, public-private partnerships. User and community representation was considered especially important where the EDIC makes a long-term promise to users.</p>

Table 2 - Summary of key findings from the analysis of legal forms (Source: authors' elaboration)

In a comparative perspective, across the interviews, the three legal models reveal different balances between flexibility, political legitimacy, and long-term sustainability. AISBLs and related association-based structures appear particularly effective during phases requiring organisational adaptability, community participation, and operational pragmatism, but they remain more exposed to financial instability and administrative fragmentation.

By contrast, ERICs provide the strongest framework for durable European coordination and formalised governance of research infrastructures, although their establishment

requires significant political negotiation, administrative capacity, and long-term governmental commitment. EDICs occupy an intermediate position, combining elements of institutional flexibility with stronger political anchoring at Member State level and a clearer orientation towards strategic European digital infrastructures. Compared with ERICs, EDICs are perceived as more adaptable and potentially faster to operationalise, yet they also raise concerns regarding governance balance, bureaucratic expansion, and regulatory uncertainty. Overall, the interviews suggest that no single model is universally optimal; rather, suitability depends on the infrastructure's maturity, political embedding, governance needs, and sustainability strategy.

These findings therefore suggest that the future Cultural Heritage Cloud could adopt different legal frameworks, transitioning from an initial temporary legal form (suitable for the need for flexibility) to a more structured, long-term one. This is indeed the basis for the proposals formulated in the WP10's Deliverable 10.2, for which this report provides data evidence.

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Annex – Dataset of coded interview transcriptions

Table 3 - AISBL (Source: authors' elaboration)

Case/Identifier	Phase	Question/theme	Summary of responses	Notes
EOSC, OPERAS	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	AISBL is practical and easy to manage; Brussels/Belgium helps lobbying and is seen as diplomatically neutral; AISBL can include international organisations as members.	Answers combine experience from creating two AISBLs: OPERAS (2019) and EOSC (2020/21).
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Compared with French loi 1901 associations, German and Dutch associations, and German gUG/gGmbH; Belgium/AISBL was preferred for perceived neutrality.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	EOSC was created quickly but COVID made establishment harder; opening a Belgian bank account is the hardest step for non-Belgians; the process requires back-and-forth with Belgium	

		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Both teams worked with a Belgian notary; a Belgian intermediary/notary made dealings with the authorities much easier.	
	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	The AISBL status is considered very convenient; the flexibility outweighed the hurdles.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: flexibility, easy statute updates, manageable contact with Belgian authorities, financial management close to the French model; Disadvantages: administrative load, bank mandates/rights, higher employer costs in Belgium.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Need a Belgian accountant and auditor; distributed offices/teams work well but require a capable HR manager for multi-country contracts/pay; managing distributed teams can be demanding.	

		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	EOSC started with a Brussels office and then moved to a distributed set-up; OPERAS has always used distributed teams, with occasional Brussels offices/meeting spaces.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	EOSC: c. 80% member/observer fees, rest EU projects; OPERAS: c. 94% EU projects and €100-150k from members; project dependence is seen as unstable; foundations/PPPs were mentioned but not yet developed.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	OPERAS: Service Provider Board meeting monthly; EOSC: several committees, added later to the statutes.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Committees that visibly involve stakeholders/member states were considered important.	

		8. How did you set up your user committees	EOSC: user committees for research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, RPOs, plus task forces; OPERAS: Assembly of Commons with sub-groups/SIGs acting mostly at service level.	
		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	Very few cross-border legal problems were reported; main practical issues are currency exchange and bank-transfer fees.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	AISBL membership can include non-EU countries; their status would change only if the entity later moved to ERIC/EDIC.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	OPERAS plans to keep the AISBL for a transitional period after ERIC creation; EOSC expects a governance-model change after 2027; the AISBL may remain but perhaps not at the head of the cloud.	

		11a. If yes, what criteria will determine the time of change?	OPERAS: reassess around ERIC renewal / usefulness after c. 5 years; EOSC: decision linked to the post-2027 governance model.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	A future European entity should solve HR difficulties; it should allow more business/economic activity or easier interfaces with company-like structures.	
MCA	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	AISBL was quickly seen as the clearest and most relevant option; international scope under Belgian law was important.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Foundation was the only real alternative briefly considered.	

	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Set-up was manageable, although administrative processes involve multiple formal steps; notaries, consultants, publication requirements, and banking transparency obligations add procedural complexity.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Used consultants, a Belgian accountant and a local acting partner; kept a Belgian office and relied on expertise in Belgian law.	
	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	For MCA, the effort was worth it.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: manageable and very flexible governance design; easy to shape stakeholder/member-state involvement; Disadvantages: Belgian administrative complexity and, in projects, stronger competition from other Belgian entities.	

		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Need a Belgian intermediary, auditor and legal office; staffing spans Belgium, France and Italy (accounting, director, policy/project management, communication, tech and general management); main office in Paris; legal office in Belgium; secondary office in Italy.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	Initially hosted by one co-founder with no direct staff; the structure was built up step by step; independence became important for advocacy; ministries later became a minority on the board.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	No mandatory model: MCA had to build its own mix; initially support came mainly from Member States; later revenues diversified through inventories/services and a mix of public and private funds.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Mandatory Board of Directors and Board of Administrators elected by the GA; committees of experts advise on specific topics.	

		8. How did you set up your user committees	User committees are essentially the members; topic-based experts/networks are mobilised depending on the project; MCA is fundamentally a members' organisation.	
		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	No major cross-border problem has been encountered under Belgian law; the AISBL works as a European international organisation and is familiar to the Commission/network environment.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Non-EU participation is possible if allowed by the statutes; no major legal obstacle was reported.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	No change of legal status is foreseen; only statutes continue to evolve.	

		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	A European employment framework/statute for staff working across countries would be very valuable.	
ARIADNE	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	After 10 years of project work, a durable international structure was needed to continue community work; AISBL was chosen for its simple bureaucracy and international character.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Irish company limited by guarantee was considered; Italy was possible, but an international structure was preferred.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Set-up was very easy and fast (about two weeks); statutes were drafted internally and finalised with a Belgian consultant/notary; opening a bank account and legal address was manageable from abroad.	

After	2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Used a Belgian consultant and local legal-address service; minor operational irritants remained (e.g. activating bank cards in Belgium).	
	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	The difficulties were worth it.	
	4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: low bureaucracy; AISBL can be tailored closely to partner needs; Disadvantage: according to the interview, the AISBL cannot coordinate EU-funded projects as easily as a company.	
	5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Board of Directors works pro bono; semi-permanent staff are paid by participating organisations; temporary teams are used for projects; no permanent AISBL posts; offices in Prato are hosted free of charge.	

		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	ARIADNE was operational from the start; there was no real separate establishment phase.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Very low member fees (€150/year) cover administrative/Belgian costs; hosting is provided pro bono; new members pay data-provision costs (around €1,000) when relevant.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Honorary members and partner-suggested experts can provide advice on specific issues.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	The General Assembly is the main participatory body; partners can submit suggestions which are implemented if feasible.	

		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	No major cross-border issue was reported; the key is to draft statutes carefully, so they do not create unnecessary territorial limits.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Non-EU participation is possible; examples mentioned: UK vice-president, Japanese and US members; associated partners in EU projects depend on the call.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	No change is envisaged; AISBL is seen as the best current solution.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	For infrastructures that are more than research-only, an ad hoc European entity/cooperative model could be worth considering.	

ECCO 1	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Need to be close to EU institutions in Brussels; practical support in Brussels mattered; AISBL was seen as the easiest form to create at the time.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	No other legal form was considered at the time.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Paperwork was difficult without a Brussels office; administrative procedures still require action in Belgium; finding legal support in Belgium has been difficult.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Historically, founders based near Brussels helped; today, life is easier if someone is physically based in Brussels and can handle administration in French.	

	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	Flexibility has become a concern; ECCO is open to reconsidering the set-up, though no formal process has started.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: Brussels presence and European visibility; Disadvantages: administrative requirements can be relatively demanding, with some banking constraints, limited flexibility, and reliance on existing administrative processes.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Board/committee elected by the GA with country representation; mandatory posts: president, vice-president, treasurer/vice-treasurer, secretaries; proportional country voting at the GA; associated members can attend but not vote; Brussels mailbox only; coworking used when needed.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	No clear stage-by-stage breakdown was given.	

		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Funding mainly from membership fees; activities are adjusted to a fixed annual budget; occasional past project money/sponsorship and in-kind venue support.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	No advisory bodies.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	The GA already represents the users/national associations; there is also a yearly presidents' meeting; no classic service-user committee exists	
		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	Belgian administration is easier when there is local presence and French-language capacity; being in Brussels is useful, but Belgium is not seen as administratively friendly.	

		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Associate membership enables non-EU members (e.g. Turkey); Switzerland can be a full member depending on profile; the UK could reapply.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Open to possible future change, but no concrete legal/status review has started. Change would concern host country, polling has already started within the association to assess openness to this.	
		11a. If yes, what criteria will determine the time of change?	It would depend on the current administrative requirements and their practical implications.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	A future European entity could aim for greater flexibility for organisations without an on-site presence; civil-society organisations could benefit from simplified organisational processes.	

ECCO 2	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Historical reasons for the AISBL choice were linked to Brussels and to the options available at the time; the interview focused mainly on current operation rather than the original set up.	Founding-stage remarks are mostly historical/entity-level; the strongest evidence concerns present-day operation under Belgian law.
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Current operation is difficult because of language barriers and Belgian bureaucracy; accounting/legal/tax processes largely require French; .lack of staff in Belgium makes compliance hard and legal advice expensive.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	ECCO relies on a Belgian bank/accountant, but this does not remove the friction; the organisation is considering whether another country/set-up would be easier.	
	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	The current arrangement creates enough burden that change is being considered; the absence of a Belgian board member/local signatory has made the situation harder.	

		<p>4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity</p>	<p>Advantages were largely tolerated because there was no other option at the time; current disadvantages include administrative procedures, language requirements, and board and banking formalities.</p>	
		<p>5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning</p>	<p>One administrative person is engaged from Portugal as a service-provider/freelancer; committee meets monthly; Belgian accounting firm is required; no formal external audit; some VAT exemptions / no VAT number.</p>	
		<p>5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage</p>	<p>No clear stage-by-stage breakdown was given.</p>	

		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Funding comes from membership fees; budget is voted by the GA and kept deliberately low; historic extra income came mainly from projects/sponsors/in-kind support.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	No advisory bodies.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	GA/delegates are the main channel for representing members/users; there are no classic user committees because ECCO does not provide user services in that sense.	
		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	The Belgian host-country legal framework entails specific operational requirements, including language, tax, and compliance obligations; limited local staffing can affect implementation capacity.	

		<p>10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions</p>	<p>Associate membership allows non-EU participation; full membership depends on the profile set by the statutes.</p>	
		<p>11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?</p>	<p>ECCO is considering whether a different country/legal set-up would be preferable, but no formal process exists yet.</p>	
		<p>11a. If yes, what criteria will determine the time of change?</p>	<p>Timing would depend on member support and the evolution of administrative requirements.</p>	
		<p>12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?</p>	<p>A future European entity could aim to simplify administrative and language-related requirements and facilitate cross-border civil-society work.</p>	

ENCATC	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	In 1998 AISBL was the only real option for partners from different countries; Brussels proximity also helped networking with EU institutions.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	No real alternative at the time; a later move to a foundation was considered but abandoned because it would create too much extra work.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Recent anti-money-laundering and transparency requirements made administrative work heavier; opening/changing bank accounts and filing board changes became more time-consuming.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	The obligations are handled as part of normal administration; despite the burden, the organisation has stayed with AISBL and adapted to the new rules.	

	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	No change is planned; although a foundation was once considered, the work needed was too great and new Belgian law now gives AISBLs more freedom.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: cross-border structure, Brussels networking, acceptable transparency obligations; Disadvantages: banking and compliance requirements, together with administrative processes requiring a significant time investment.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Administrative work plus occasional use of consultants; rented Brussels office; 6 staff; accountant and external auditor; having someone from Belgium / local signatory is strongly recommended.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	No stage-by-stage breakdown was given.	

		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	c. 70% EU funds; c. 15% membership income; c. 15% income-generating activities; fundraising is currently being explored to diversify revenue sources.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Board of Directors with members from different countries; gender balance is important; group of partner presidents under MoUs; statutes allow advisory people/bodies.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Diverse board composition and independent leadership are key governance elements.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	Highly participatory approach: members help define activities; feedback is collected through surveys and external evaluation.	

		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	AISBL makes it relatively easy to apply for EU projects and work with many kinds of institutions.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Many members are outside Europe; no major legal difficulty was reported beyond national administrative issues.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	No change envisaged.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	Flexibility in the statutes is key.	

Table 4 – Foundations/Associations under Dutch Law (Source: authors' elaboration)

Case/Identifier	Phase	Question/theme	Summary of responses	Notes
EF	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Not-for-profit independent body; had to be able to receive funds and employ people; seat selection between several national laws was part of the choice.	Harry Verwayen was not yet at EF when the foundation was set up, so founding-stage answers are partial/reconstructed.
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Different seat options (Netherlands, Belgium, France) were considered; the Dutch foundation form was ultimately chosen.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	No major implementation hurdle was recalled; the main issue was deciding under which national law to establish the foundation.	

	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	No reason to revisit the choice was identified in the interview.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantage: independence; Disadvantage: being a non-profit can make collaboration/commercialisation with for-profit actors more complex; a separate commercial arm would be the likely solution if needed, however, commercialisation does not really align with EF's identity.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Rented office space in the Royal Library of the Netherlands; around 60 employees; strong relationships across the ecosystem are important.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	No stage-by-stage breakdown was given.	

		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Mainly financed via the contract with the European Commission (c. 90%); additional funded projects; key risk is losing the next contract or the funding line itself.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Advisory Board including representatives from ENA and EAF.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	EF changed over the years, e.g. used to have a Governing Board and now has a Supervisory Board and a separate Advisory Board. What matters is having people who keep the organisation aligned with its values and current sector developments.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	Aggregators are involved through a Data Quality Committee, working groups and task forces.	

		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	Dutch foundation law supports EF's independence; annual reporting does not need to be in Dutch; having staff in other countries is possible but adds payroll/tax/pension complexity.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	No major legal constraint was seen for non-EU collaboration; EC contractual obligations may nonetheless require priority for EU Member States in some contexts.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	No change was discussed.	
ENA	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	ENA was formalised so the network could continue independently if EF funding stopped; the association format suits a membership-based democratic network.	Juha Henriksson was not part of ENA's original set-up; his answers mainly describe the current governance model.

		<p>1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those</p>	<p>Membership logic was likely decisive; Dutch association law offers a relatively lightweight formal governance structure.</p>	
	<p>During</p>	<p>2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles</p>		<p>ENA came later, initially only an informal network around the foundation; third pillar, the Europeana Aggregators' Forum (EAF), is not a legal entity; EC has always "owned" the initiative for Europeana – in the context of the data space, this is currently established in the form of the Expert Group on the data space for cultural heritage (CEDCHE)</p>

		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: lightweight formal governance with a democratic Members Council; Disadvantages: ENA remains heavily dependent on EF and, in its current set-up, cannot itself receive/manage project funding.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	No ENA staff; voluntary Management Board (6), Members Council (36) and Community Steering Groups; day-to-day support relies heavily on EF staff and an ENA secretariat hosted by EF.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	No stage-by-stage breakdown was given.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	No independent funding model was described; ENA currently depends on EF for financial administration and operational support.	

		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Members Council and community structure are the key participatory/governance bodies mentioned.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Democratic member representation through the Members Council is central.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	The seven Communities function similarly to user committees, with members contributing their expertise.	
		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	Dutch association law is relatively lightweight; the statutes created a democratic process beyond the legal minimum.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Individual membership makes non-EU participation easy; many members come from outside the EU.	

		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	No change was discussed.	
APEF	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Dutch foundation was preferred because an association was not workable for national archives; foundation offered independence and transparent governance; closeness to Europeana also mattered.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Belgium was considered as an alternative seat; the Netherlands was chosen for geographical closeness to Europeana.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Main implementation issue was negotiating differentiated contributions; the sustainability model was prepared through APENet/APEX project work.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Business-planning/sustainability work packages under earlier projects helped prepare the foundation model.	

		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: independent and lightweight structure with transparent governance; Disadvantages: contribution-setting is politically delicate and income cannot be generated from the content itself.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Assembly of associates keeps decision power (c. 30 institutions); lightweight set-up with two core staff plus part-time development/system/security roles; postal address in The Hague, remote work, Dutch accountant, Dutch-speaking support for statutes/governance.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	No stage-by-stage breakdown was given.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or	Institutional contributions depend on GDP; fees cover maintenance/network/updating; new functionalities are funded through projects;	

		funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	growth in income depends largely on adding more associates.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	No formal advisory board; working groups play that role (country managers, standards, sustaining services/new functionalities).	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Working groups around standards and service sustainability are the key bodies highlighted.	
		9. For AISBL/National Non-Profits/Similar: How have national legal frameworks of your host country influenced your ability to operate cross-border	Dutch law is manageable cross-border but the official legal version of the statutes must be in Dutch; cross-border employment is handled with external HR offices in England and Germany.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or	No legal problem was identified for non-EU associates; Switzerland, Norway and Iceland are associates; content from outside the EU is possible if linked to European history.	

		collaborate and under what conditions		
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	No change was discussed.	

Table 5 - ERIC (Source: authors' elaboration)

Case	Phase	Question/theme	Summary of responses	Notes
E-RIHS	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Flexibility; long-term commitment from Member States; European added value through EC/MS cooperation.	Choice followed a comparative legal analysis; in addition to the primary interviewee further remarks came from an ECHOES member who also worked on E-RIHS.
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Comparative analysis of legal forms was prepared; GmbH was also discussed as an alternative.	

	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Implementation was long and negotiation-heavy; strict interpretation of the ERIC regulation caused a stop; ICCROM's role delayed the EC decision by c. 2-3 years.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	ICCROM needed to temporarily step back from the requesting institutions and re-joined after establishment; continuous dialogue/negotiation with the EC; strong support from host-country and other national ministries.	
	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	Difficulties were worth it; choice was also driven by ESFRI/policy-makers and funding members.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: long-term commitment, cross-border cooperation, common approach, single entry point to services; Disadvantages: ERIC still follows the national law of the seat; fragmentation across countries remains challenging.	

		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Strong staff and time commitment are needed, especially in the creation phase; distributed infrastructures do not necessarily need major real estate; funding typically combines membership fees and projects.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	Set-up: intensive time, staff effort and political/legal negotiation; Early operations: membership/in-kind/project mechanisms had to be organised; Operational stage: maintain staff and quality system; premises optional unless strategically useful.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Membership fees; in-kind contributions; European/national/regional projects; private donor support; HQ building made available free of use for 10 years by a bank foundation.	

		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board central to the quality system and strategy; User Representation Working Group (outside the statutes) to engage users.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board is a clear must-have; Committee of National Nodes / General Assembly type structures are also key for ERIC governance.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	User Representation Working Group; user meetings and co-creation workshops (e.g. around the Digilab).	
		9. For ERIC/EDIC/Similar: How do you manage the relationship between the host country and other member states	Very strong host-country commitment is vital; regular meetings with ministries to solve day-to-day issues; Italian framework worked relatively well, though hiring/VAT questions remain.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or	Cooperation beyond the EU is possible through strategic cooperation agreements;	

		collaborate and under what conditions	examples mentioned: Brazil and Egypt.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Seen as a long-term structure; no status change envisaged at this early stage.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	A new European entity should secure long-term Member State commitment; alignment with European and national roadmaps is important.	
DARIAH	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	ERIC fit a genuinely cross-border initiative; Member States as members gave long-term commitment and reliability; at the time, ERIC was a new and accessible model.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	No real alternative was seriously studied.	

	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Long implementation path (ESFRI roadmap 2006 -> ERIC 2014); creating an ERIC can take 5–10 years; major issue is bridging the gap between project end and ERIC establishment.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Used/recommended a transitional legal structure and transitional funding to keep the infrastructure alive; national commitment must be built ministry by ministry and takes time.	
	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	ERIC is well suited to DARIAH's purpose; difficulties were worth it; growth from 15 founding countries to 24 confirms the fit.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: long-term commitment and a European framework for cooperation; Disadvantages: HR/accounting/legal matters still depend on the host country's law; changing statutes becomes increasingly difficult as membership grows.	

		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Needs a minimum administrative core (finance, HR, personnel); cash and in-kind support from countries are important; member contributions alone are often insufficient; EU projects remain necessary.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	Set-up: a bridge structure/funding was needed between projects and ERIC establishment; Early operations: basic administration had to be tied to core needs; Full operations: combine member contributions with EU projects and national support.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Cash and in-kind contributions from member countries; European projects; national support; looking at donations/private-sector support, though this requires capacity.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	General Assembly with national representatives; Board of Directors;	

		National Coordination Committee; Scientific Board; Senior Management Team and bottom-up Working Groups.	
	7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	General Assembly and Board of Directors are essential; scientific and national coordination bodies are also key.	
	8. How did you set up your user committees	No separate user committee; bottom-up Working Groups represent the community and raise topics/issues.	
	9. For ERIC/EDIC/Similar: How do you manage the relationship between the host country and other member states	In the absence of a clearly defined framework, certain issues may require engagement with the relevant authorities; HR, VAT, finance, and legal matters typically involve ongoing administrative interaction.	
	10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	The structure encourages collaboration outside Europe; examples mentioned: US and Egypt.	

		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Legal form seen as appropriate/final; only statutes need periodic adjustment.	
		11a. If yes, what criteria will determine the time of change?	Statutes may be revised when adaptation becomes necessary, although in practice such changes are complex, time-consuming and new members need to agree on existing statutes.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	Any new entity should preserve long-term commitment while allowing broad international cooperation.	
CLARIN	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Sustainable long-term structure for a virtual, distributed infrastructure.	CLARIN expert joined at a later stage; most specific input concerned current functioning and international cooperation.

	After	3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	ERIC is regarded as the sustainable long-term structure for the infrastructure.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: distributed model can rely on universities for recruitment and premises; Disadvantages: central membership fees alone are not enough; strong coordination capacity is needed.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Virtual distributed infrastructure; agreements with universities for hiring and hosting; enough coordination staff plus centralised committee support; c. 70 people overall, with c. 10 in coordination.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	No detailed phase breakdown was given; operationally, the key needs are university agreements, coordination staff and harmonised committee support.	

		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Membership fees; host fee from the Netherlands; ministry funding linked to successful EU funding; in-kind time contributions; other project money for ERICs; diversification pursued without sponsorship.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	General Assembly; Scientific Advisory Board; Board of Directors; permanent committees (National Coordinators Forum; Technical Centres Committee); thematic committees; Knowledge Infrastructure, Legal/Ethical and Technical Centre Assessment committees; ambassadors.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	General Assembly; Scientific Advisory Board; strong board/technical coordination structures.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	No separate standalone user committee was emphasised; user involvement is channelled through a User Involvement Committee and country-based representation.	

		9. For ERIC/EDIC/Similar: How do you manage the relationship between the host country and other member states	The Netherlands works well as host because the administration is familiar with ERICs; Brexit created major hassle for UK relations; Switzerland was also difficult.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Several frameworks are possible: simple MoUs/expertise exchange, or third-country agreements with payment; South Africa was described as smooth; Australia/India were mentioned in lighter cooperation formats	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Seen as a sustainable long-term structure; no status change planned.	
		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	In a crowded landscape, a new entity needs a very clear value proposition and stakeholder case.	

Table 6 - EDIC (Source: authors' elaboration)

Case	Phase	Question/theme	Summary of responses	Notes
ALT-EDIC	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	EDIC fit the project's goal of bringing industry closer to governments; model matched the project from the start; ALT-EDIC was part of the first batch of EDICs.	
		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	No alternative was considered; the project was conceived as an EDIC from the outset.	
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Creation was demanding because Member States had to be convinced and statutes/documents negotiated; implementation in France required a national legal structure to operate locally.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	France informed and involved the competent administration early (DGE);	

			a French association mirroring the EDIC statutes was created to open bank accounts and launch activities; once approved, publication was very fast.	
After		3. If aware of hurdles earlier - another type of entity chosen OR were difficulties worth it	Difficulties were worth it; after creation, operations ran smoothly and the team/project portfolio grew quickly	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: flexible governance; close links with the private sector; Disadvantages: unresolved VAT/economic-activity/state-aid questions; need for a national implementing structure.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Hosting agreement with CMN in Villers-Cotterêts; core team: director, admin manager, communications manager, legal manager; plus technical/IT/software staff and project managers; only permanent contracts are used.	

		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	Set-up: multi-state proposal, statutes, financial/governance files and negotiation; Early operations: create the national implementation vehicle and core team; Operational stage: growth of technical staff and project management capacity.	
		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Member contributions (minimum linked to GNI); European projects; roughly 50/50 split between MS contributions and EU projects	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Scientific committee is being set up to involve research stakeholders.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	No fixed must-have list was given; governance is considered highly adaptable under the EDIC model.	

		9. For ERIC/EDIC/Similar: How do you manage the relationship between the host country and other member states	No major problems were reported between France and other member states despite the French implementation via an association; EDIC recognition and political legitimacy helped.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Membership is open to EU Member States and countries associated with the Digital Programme; security requirements are strict; ownership/control issues can trigger lengthy negotiations.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Seen as the final legal form.	
DIGITAL COMMONS	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	EDIC chosen for 'institutional capital' and a sustainability promise backed by Member States; voice of Member States seen as a safeguard against monopoly/abuse; governance should reflect the promise made to users.	This interview focused mainly on governance philosophy and political positioning; many operational/financial questions were not answered in detail.

		1a. Other types of legal entities considered/factors that influenced decision not to choose those	Started from a French SCIC cooperative model with colleges/community representation; also operated for a time via an MoU with a few committed states; EDIC was preferred for stronger State commitment and European recognition.	
During		2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Initial outreach to Member States was ineffective because the message was unclear; after France, Germany and the Netherlands built a convincing prototype, the EDIC was created in six months.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Clarified the narrative and built a prototype EDIC with supportive states and communities; administrative procedures remain a potential operational risk.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Advantages: institutional backing, sustainability signal, flexibility/adaptability; Disadvantages: risk of increasing procedural complexity and administrative fragmentation.	

		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Main requirement stressed was not staffing but governance discipline; clear purpose, open-source orientation and conflict-management between members were seen as essential.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Founders should be in a minority position vis-à-vis users; user-interest protection should sit at the core of governance.	
		8. How did you set up your user committees	Users/communities should have real weight in governance; no separate user-committee architecture was detailed.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	The EDIC is not seen as fixed once and for all; it should adapt to the needs of its board and users.	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Future evolution should be driven by the needs of the board/users.	

		12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?	A new European entity should make a clear, durable promise to users; governance must protect users and avoid founder capture; open, non-proprietary infrastructure is important.	
EBRAINS	Before	1. Specific qualities that you were looking for/that made you choose this type of entity	Current AISBL is a transitional form; move to EDIC was strongly encouraged by the Commission / DG CONNECT; EDIC is seen as quicker to establish than an ERIC and better aligned with dedicated calls.	Interview reflects EBRAINS' transition from a current AISBL to the planned EDIC.
	During	2. How would you qualify the implementation process/any unexpected hurdles	Main hurdle was identifying the right national ministerial contacts in each Member State; overall EDIC-building is time-consuming and requires extensive inter-state / inter-ministerial coordination.	
		2a. If hurdles, which ones/how addressed them	Worked through EBRAINS national representatives in 9-12 countries to find the right contacts;	

			Board of Government Representatives meetings were used to validate project, finance, statutes, governance and policy documents.	
		4. Main advantages/disadvantages of this legal entity	Expected EDIC advantages: stronger EU positioning and access to dedicated calls; openness to public-private partnerships; Disadvantage/challenge: current EDIC KPIs are primarily oriented toward operational activities outside the research context.	
		5. Requirements and needs of this legal entity in terms of functioning	Brussels central office for administration, HR, finance and project management; Management Board (5) plus Governing Board (7); Scientific Advisory Committee with one country representative each; c. €2-2.5M/year needed for functioning costs.	
		5a. What was needed at which stage - during the set-up, the early operational, and the fully operational stage	Set-up required extensive documentation and intergovernmental coordination; Current operations rely on central Brussels administration and a scientific/technical management core.	

		6. How is entity financially sustained/what business model, revenue streams or funding mechanisms necessary to ensure its stability	Project-based funding (first project c. €36M with 52 partners; second similar project expected); country/node contributions (€50k-€100k, sometimes adapted to GNI); national/institutional and in-kind contributions cover core functioning.	
		7. How did you set up your advisory bodies	Scientific Advisory Committee; Management Board; Governing Board.	
		7a. Which bodies would you consider must-haves	Scientific and governing boards appear central; no separate must-have list was given.	
		10. To what extent possible for non-EU or associated countries to participate or collaborate and under what conditions	Industrial/private partners may join if useful to the infrastructure; restrictions for some associated/non-EU actors have been eased (e.g. Switzerland).	
		11. Legal entity is final OR are you looking to evolve/to change status?	Current AISBL is transitional; the aim is to move to EDIC status.	

		<p>11a. If yes, what criteria will determine the time of change?</p>	<p>Timing is linked to completing the transition and realising the benefits of the EDIC framework.</p>	
		<p>12. Recommendations for the creation of a new type of European legal entity: what kind of qualities or characteristics would you like to see?</p>	<p>During creation and operation, ethics, IP and KPI design should be thought through early and adapted to research realities.</p>	